

BIOMECHANICAL RATIONALE FOR USING CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER SPACERS FOR LUMBAR INTERBODY FUSION—A FINITE ELEMENT STUDY

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1. Introduction

Interbody fusion is the most reliable fusion technique currently available for the lumbar spine. These constructs are biomechanically stronger than those used in posterolateral arthrodesis and produce a better biologic fusion [1-2]. Interbody fusion permits high load transmission through the anterior column, restoration of disc height and segmental lordosis, and requires a minimal bone graft volume [2]. The goals of the posterior lumbar interbody fusion procedure using cages/spacers with posterior instrumentation and graft bone are to stabilize the motion segment and facilitate the fusion process. These spacers were initially manufactured using either medical grade stainless steel or titanium alloys. Recent advances in the medical implant industry have resulted in using medical grade carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP). A claimed advantage and the driving force in support of using CFRP is that its Young's modulus ("E" = 9 GPa) is much closer to that of cortical bone ("E" = 12 GPa), as compared to titanium ("E" = 110 GPa). The biomechanical advantages of this difference are not fully understood [3]. Dijk et al investigated the effect of cage stiffness on the rate of lumbar interbody fusion using poly-(L-lactic acid) and titanium cages [4]. Poly-(L-lactic acid) ("E" = 4.2 GPa) and titanium cages ("E" = 110 GPa) were implanted in the L3_L4, level of Dutch milk goats. A 6-month follow-up of the goats performed using radiographs indicated that the less stiff, poly-(L-lactic acid) cages significantly enhanced the rate of interbody fusion, as compared with that of the titanium cages. In formulating the present study, our hypothesis is that a CFRP spacer with posterior instrumentation provides stability similar to titanium spacer with posterior instrumentation but allows larger loads to go through

the bone graft and reduces the stresses on the bony endplates. The purpose of this study was to evaluate this hypothesis by comparing the biomechanical performance of a posterior lumbar interbody fusion spacer made of CFRP with the commonly used titanium spacer, using the finite element approach.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Intact Model

A three-dimensional (3D) nonlinear FE model of the lumbar spine that consisted of four lumbar vertebrae, three intervertebral discs, and associated spinal ligaments was developed. Geometrical details of the human lumbar spine (L2-L5) were obtained from high-resolution computed tomography (CT) images of a 46-year-old male subject who had no spinal deformities. Digital CT data were imported to a software program (Mimics; Materialise Inc., Leuven, Belgium) that was used to generate the 3-dimensional geometrical surface of the lumbar spine. Exported IGES files from the Mimics software were input into Unigraphics NX 3.0 (Siemens PLM Software, Torrance, CA) to form solid models for each vertebral segment. The solid model was then imported into Hypermesh 8.0 (Altair Engineering, Inc., Troy, MI) to generate FE meshes. The FE method was analyzed with commercially available software (ABAQUS 6.6-1; Hibbitt, Karlsson and Sorenson, Inc., Providence, RI).

Three-dimensional homogenous and transversely isotropic solid elements were used to model the cortical and cancellous cores, the posterior bony parts of the vertebrae. The anterior longitudinal ligament, posterior longitudinal ligament, intertransverse ligament, ligament flavum, capsular ligament, interspinous ligament, and supraspinous ligament were modeled using tension-only truss elements.

2.2 Material properties

Material properties were selected based on various literature sources (Table.1.)[5]. The cortical and cancellous regions of the vertebrae were modeled independently. Differentiation between cortical and trabecular bone in the posterior region was difficult to delineate; therefore, the posterior elements were all assigned a single set of material properties.

Table.1. Material properties in the present FE models

Component	Young's modulus (MPa)	Cross-section n (mm^2)	Poisson's ratio
Cortical bone	$E_x = 11300$ $E_y = 11300$ $E_z = 22000$ $G_x = 3800$ $G_y = 5400$ $G_z = 5400$		$\nu_{xy} = 0.484$ $\nu_{xz} = 0.203$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.203$
Cancellous bone	$E_x = 140$ $E_y = 140$ $E_z = 200$ $G_x = 48.3$ $G_y = 48.3$ $G_z = 48.3$		$\nu_{xy} = 0.45$ $\nu_{xz} = 0.315$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.315$
Posterior elements	3500		0.25
Disc			
Nucleus pulposus	1.0		0.4999
Annulus (ground substance)	4.2		0.45
Annulus fiber	358 – 550		0.30
Cartilaginous endplate	24.0		0.40
Ligaments			
Anterior longitudinal	7.8(<12%) 20(>12%)	63.7	
Posterior longitudinal	10(<11%) 20(>11%)	20.0	
Ligamentum flavum	15(<6.2%) 19.5(>6.2%)	40.0	
Capsular	7.5(<25%) 32.9(>25%)	30.0	
Interspinous	10(<14%) 11.6(>14%)	40.0	
Supraspinous	8.0 (<20%) 15(>20%)	30.0	
Intertransverse	10(<18%) 58.7(>18%)	1.8	
Fusion mass	3500		0.25
Pedicle screws, rod (Ti6Al4V)	110000		0.3

The annulus fibrosus was modeled as a composite of a solid matrix with embedded fibers (via the REBAR parameter) in concentric rings surrounding a nucleus pulposus, which was considered to be an incompressible inviscid fluid. Element members with hybrid formulation (C3D8H) combined with low elastic modulus and large Poisson ratio definitions were applied to simulate the nucleus pulposus. Eight-node brick elements were employed to model the matrix of the ground substance. Each of four concentric rings of ground substance contained two evenly spaced layers of annulus fibers oriented at $\pm 30^\circ$ to horizontal. The reinforcement structure annulus fibers were represented by truss elements with modified tension-only elasticity. In the radial direction, four double cross-linked fiber layers were defined, and those fibers were bounded by the annulus ground substance and both endplates. In addition, these fibers had proportionally decreased elastic strength from the outermost (550 MPa) to the innermost (358 MPa) layer [6].

The articulating facet joint surfaces were modeled using surface-to-surface contact elements in combination with the penalty algorithm with normal contact stiffness of 200 N/mm and a friction coefficient of zero. The thickness of the cartilage layer of the facet joint was assumed to be 0.2 mm. The initial gap between the cartilage layers was assumed to be 0.5 mm. The cartilage was assumed to be isotropic, linear elastic with a Young's modulus of 35 MPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.4 [7]. Spinal ligaments were represented with nonlinear material properties. Naturally changing ligament stiffness (initially low stiffness at low strains, followed by increasing stiffness at higher strains) was simulated through a "hypoelastic" material designation (Table 1). Three-dimensional truss elements were used to simulate ligaments, which were active only in tension.

2.3 Model of the Intervertebral Cage (spacer) and Posterior Instrumentation.

The convex profile and teeth were included in the solid model. CFRP ("E" = 9 GPa) and titanium ("E"=110 GPa) material properties were assigned to the spacer model to simulate spacers of 2 different stiffnesses. TSRH pedicle screws (Medtronic Sofamor Danek, Memphis, TN) (55-mm long, 6.5-mm diameter) and rod (50-mm long) instrumentation were modeled in ABAQUS. The intact L2–L5 finite

element model was modified to simulate the spacer placement using the posterior approach by removing: (1) the spinous and intraspinal ligaments, ligamentum flavum across the L4–L5 functional spinal unit (FSU); (2) 40% of the L4 spinous processes and laminae; and (3) nucleus removal through a 7.5-mm window bilaterally from the midline of the anulus. The “Distraction-Compression” principle was then simulated. A 98N distraction force was applied to the L4 vertebral bottom endplate to distract the L4 vertebra by 2 mm to accommodate the CFRP vertebral spacer. The spacers were symmetrically placed about the mid sagittal plane. Filling the space between the spacers using C3D8 elements simulated bone graft (“E”= 12 GPa) packed between the spacers in the intervertebral space. The pedicle screws were positioned such that they engage into two thirds of the vertebral body. (Fig.1)

Fig.1. Implanted model current study

2.4 Loading and Boundary Conditions.

The loading condition was the hybrid testing protocol, which was implemented during the flexibility testing of the FE models as described by Goel et al [8] for the study of adjacent level biomechanics. The follower load technique was used to simulate the vector sum of trunk muscle co-activation by using a single internal force vector that acts tangent to the curvature of the spine passing through each segmental center of rotation. This “follower” path acts tangent to the curvature of the spine, thus

mimicking the physiologic compressive loads on the lumbar spine seen in vivo. The 400 N compressive follower loads was simulated at each motion segment in the model by a pair of 2-node thermo-isotropic truss elements.

Fig.2. Lateral view of the finite element model showing follower load trusses at each level

The trusses were attached bilaterally to the cortical shell of the vertebrae at each motion segment. (Fig.2) Each truss spans the disc space passing through the instantaneous center of rotation at each motion segment. This hybrid testing protocol involved the application of the pure moment to the intact and two fusion models until the L2-L5 rotation (displacement) equaled the intact load control case values, which was achieved by imposing of 7.5 Nm extension and torsion moments on the L2 vertebral body in the intact model.

3. Results & Conclusions

The intact L3-L5 model was validated in our laboratory, as reported in our prior publications [9]. Fig. 3 is a comparison of the relative motion for the intact, CFRP spacer with instrumentation and titanium spacer with instrumentation models in response to a 400-N axial compression and a 7.5 Nm bending moment. The relative angular motion across L4/5 FSU decreased for all loading cases with the spacer and instrumentation. The relative motion across the L4/5 FSU was less than 0.5° for all loading cases with the spinal instrumentation and was similar for both types of spacer materials. Fig. 4 is a comparison of the peak centroidal Von Mises stresses seen on the endplates for a 400N compression and a 7.5 N m bending moment in various loading conditions for spines with CFRP and titanium spacers

along with posterior instrumentation.

Fig.3. Comparison of angular motion across L4 –L5 for a 400-N compression and a 6 Nm bending moment for intact spine, spine with CFRP spacer and instrumentation

The stresses in the endplate increased at least by 2.5-fold when a titanium spacer was used in the place of a CFRP spacer. A max-mum stress of 48 MPa was seen by the endplate in bending for the spine with titanium spacer and instrumentation, as compared to 20 MPa for the CFRP spacer and instrumentation case. When used in conjunction with posterior instrumentation, spacers of lesser stiffness, like CFRP, provide initial stability similar to titanium spacers, might minimize the chances of subsidence, and would lead to higher stresses in the bone graft itself. Further clinical studies on the effect of CFRP spacers on stability, subsidence, and other clinically relevant parameters are warranted to validate the observations of the current finite element study.

Fig.4 Comparison of peak von Mises stresses on L4 inferior endplate for a 400N compression and a 7.5 Nm bending moment for spine with CFRP spacer and instrumentation, and spine with titanium spacer and instrumentation.

Fig.5 is a comparison of the peak centroidal Von Mises stresses seen by the bone graft for a 400N compression and a 7.5Nm bending moment in various loading conditions for spines with CFRP and titanium spacers along with posterior instrumentation. The stresses in the bone graft increased by 9-fold in extension and rotation, 11-fold in flexion, and 15-fold in bending with a CFRP spacer as compared to the regular titanium spacer.

Fig.4. Comparison of peak von Mises stresses on L4 inferior endplate for a 400-N compression and a 6 Nm bending moment for spine with CFRP spacer and instrumentation

Fig.5. Comparison of peak von Mises stresses in graft bone for a 400-N compression and a 7.5 Nm bending moment for spine with CFRP spacer and instrumentation, and spine with titanium spacer and instrumentation

4. Discussion & Conclusions

We undertook a finite element investigation to study the effect of the spacer material property on the motion, modes. Such an investigation is not feasible in a cadaver model due to inability to estimate stresses in various spinal structures. The results from the finite element study indicate that the stress magnitude in the endplate region was lesser for the CFRP spacer as compared to the titanium spacer. The smaller stresses in the CFRP spacer case might result in lesser subsidence of the spacers into the

endplate and the adjoining cancellous bone over time. As the graft is stiffer (“E” = 12 GPa) than the CFRP spacer (“E” = 9 GPa) the graft sees higher stresses than the CFRP spacer. As the titanium spacer (“E” = 110 GPa) is stiffer than the bone graft (“E” = 12 GPa), it will stress shield the bone graft with likely implications on the rate of fusion in accordance with Wolff’s law. The CFRP spacer in a way acts to keep the bone graft (higher stiffness compared to CFRP) in place and allows the graft to take higher loads/stresses.

The predicted motion data following spacer placement with posterior instrumentation suggests that the stability provided by the spacer is independent of the material properties, but the load transfer and related parameters are different. These parameters favor the use of CFRP spacers over the titanium spacers, as shown above. While titanium spacers prevent adequate radiographic demonstration of fusion, CFRP being a radiolucent polymer allows a clear assessment of bony fusion. When used in conjunction with posterior instrumentation, spacers of lesser stiffness, like CFRP, provide initial stability similar to titanium spacers, might minimize the chances of subsidence, and would lead to higher stresses in the bone graft itself.

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